

Influence Of Environmental Perceived Quality And Risk On Environmental Satisfaction And Trust

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 30, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July 31, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Environmental Perceived Quality, Environmental Perceived Risk, Environmental Satisfaction, Environmental Trust, Green Marketing.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5150532</p>	<p><i>Purpose: This study aims to explain the relationship between Environmental Perceived Quality (EPQ), Environmental Perceived Risk (EPR), Environmental Satisfaction (ES) and Environmental Trust (ET).</i></p> <p><i>Methodology and Design: Objective of present research article is to explore influence of EPQ and risk on environmental satisfaction and trust of consumers of electronic and automobile products in Pakistan. Empirical investigations have been made to test the relationship between variables by means of surveys and questionnaires. Structural Equation Modelling is used to examine proposed theoretical framework.</i></p> <p><i>Findings: The present research indicates EPQ encounters both the severe environmental rules and regulations but also prevalent consumer ecology and environmentalism, and enrich environmental satisfaction and ET. All hypotheses made in this study were accepted.</i></p> <p><i>Conclusion: This study spreads the ET in the arena of ecological and environmental management and demonstrates that there is a significant relationship of ET with EPQ and environmental perceived risk.</i></p>

Introduction

Environmental concern has quickly risen as a standard thought owing to a dangerous atmospheric deviation these days. As a result, more foresighted associations might want to make the most of the Green opportunities. Over centuries, the issue of environmental safeguarding has been on the highest point of the driving force of worldwide and universal concerns as a stand-out amongst the most significant issues at both the national and international levels; organizations are required to give careful consideration to promote green products. (Kalafatis and Pollard, 1999). It is also a fact that environment impacts almost every aspect of our lives. There is hardly any sector that is not influenced by the environment. The present research will make an impact on the present circumstances in various sectors.

Previous research has emphasized the associated issues regarding trust, ignoring some key suggestions in this regard. There is hardly any research in the said area. Therefore, this study has attempted to fill the gap by using the above arrangement Chen (2013). The present research has addressed new variables in the said area. ET is more significant for companies under the framework of stricter environmental regulations and more dominant consumer ecology and environmentalism. The trust factor is also one of the major concerns in all sectors. Talking about the ET, the researchers have tried to find out its relationship with other variables. Perceived quality is defined as the consumers' judgment about an entity's services containing overall excellence or superiority (Snoj et al., 2004). Chen and Chang (2013) proposed a novel construct, "green perceived quality", although environmental consciousness is more popular.

This paper has attempted to combine the earlier work on Green marketing with the novel management research framework of ET. Further, this research applies an observed study to test the relationships among variables used. This study has intended to create a new framework agreement on ET, the universal tendency of the environment in order to improve the company's trust. According to the Artto&Kujala (2020) framework, when multiple firms participate in a single project, that project is large and complex and includes many risks. Moreover, Aaltonen, 2019; Engelke et al., 2019; Mourão et al. (2018)) depicted that nowadays, the requirements of external stakeholder's form one of the greatest causes of risk and uncertainty within a project.

Nowadays, environmental concern has gained a particular attention and it has increasingly emerged as a conventional notion in the wake of global warming. Such a notion, particularly, grasps the developing countries

such as Islamic Republic of Pakistan. In addition, there is less attention to the area of consumers' green consciousness in Pakistan. Therefore, the major objectives of the present research explore constructs namely environment perceived quality and environment perceived risk in an attempt to augment ET and environmental satisfaction.

Furthermore, Environmental Satisfaction has also been shown to significantly affect retention (Balouch & Hassan, 2014; Holston-Okae, 2017; Markey, Ravenswood, & Webber, 2012).

1. Literature and Hypothesis

Today's consumers have paid significant attention towards global environmental degradation. McIntosh (1991). This context, holds that consumers are more attentive towards the growth of environmental guard activities. These days, consumers favor those products and services that are environment friendly. There are number of examples of certain products and services that are environment friendly. Furthermore, this idea is getting rapid popularity throughout the world. The concept of Green marketing incorporates all marketing activities including the establishment of environmental protection to encourage and maintain customer attitudes and behavior (Jain and Kaur, 2004). Referring to the Prior researches, Jain and Kaur (2004) assert that companies should utilize and implement green marketing approaches to find out customers' environmental needs, to promote eco label products, to segment and target green market into different niches, to target one or several niche markets, to communicate green positioning strategies, and to device a green marketing mix program in the companies. Ultimately, companies must change their business models to meet consumer business and the popularity of environmentally friendly (Ottman, 1992, Peattie, 1995). Therefore, as Porter and Linde (1995) as well as Chen et al. (2006) claim, to attain competitive edge, it is important that organizations need to use green marketing. Therefore, it also helps not only saving the environment but also impact on other factors as well. Consumers using green marketing's products and services are better aware about markets and other relevant circumstances. Perceived quality is consumer perception to whole quality or excellence of the product or service as well as consumer expected (Aaker, 2013). Therefore, perceived quality is more significant in these days (Sweeney et al., 1999, Zeithaml, 1988; Aaker, 1996, Parasuraman et al., 1988). Because environmental awareness is more dominant at the moment, we propose a unique concept, "EPQ", and refer to Zeithaml (1988) to define it as "the customer's perception about a brand's (or a product's) overall environmental excellence or superiority". When the customers' perceptions precisely meet their expectations, the expectations are confirmed. In consumers' markets, there exists variety of companies. This derive on the part of such companies is based the consumers' expectations (Parasuraman et al., 1988, Olsen, 2002, Sweeney et al., 1999; Tsiaotso, 2006; Arifin & Fachrodji, 2015, Edison & Restuti, 2014).

H1. EPQ has positive association with environmental satisfaction.

Consumers' decision to make purchases is not simple. Instead, purchase decisions frequently involve risks (Rao et al., 2007). Therefore, making a purchase decision is a lot more complex than generally people think about it. This purchase decision also becomes riskier when the results of wrong decisions are highly negative. Hence, purchasers need to know the type and level of risk involved in each of their purchases. According to Peter and Ryan (1976), Perceived risk, which is an independent approximation and assessment by consumers, is associated with possible significances of incorrect purchase decision. This is also really important as this perception is based on number of factors. Based on the researches of Peter and Ryan, 1976, Eid, 2011, Wood and Scheer, 1996, Jacoby and Kaplan, 1972, Sweeney et al., 1999, the researcher has developed the hypotheses:

H2. EPR is negatively related with environmental satisfaction.

In simplest words, trust means I know in advance what you will do in future. In almost all decisions, trust has the most important impact hence purchasers value it more. Furthermore, trust, as the certain degree of confidence in the other party, will perform as expected (Schurr and Ozanne, 1985, Rotter, 1971).

ET is a readiness to depend on trustworthy, generous beliefs or expectations, leading to a product or service, based on the ability of the relevant performance. As these expectations on certain products and services performance is another significant factor. Generally, people's expectations are not realistic in many cases therefore it becomes much challenging. There are number of competitors hence satisfying your customers better than others is really challenging (Chen, 2010, 2013)). In case of a satisfactory understanding of consumers, the consumers would develop a sophisticated level of trust, affiliation with their vendors or buyers. It is therefore necessary that satisfaction and trust are related with each other. Efforts are required to not only satisfy our customers but also keep the trust.

H3. Environmental satisfaction is positively related with environmental trust.

Theoretical framework

EPQ is independent variable which has positive influence on Environmental satisfaction another independent variable is EPR which has negative impact on Environmental Satisfaction. Environmental satisfaction has a positive effect on ET which is dependent variable.

2. Methodology

The researchers have used research instrument comprising of questionnaires and interviews. These instruments are effective in primary data collection. The respondents of this research are the university students having background of management sciences who have the awareness regarding research areas of this research. The researchers used self-administered questionnaire to collect primary data from 100 consumer of electronic and automobile products because electronic and automobile products have to meet strict environmental rules and regulation, so purchasers are more inclined towards products having ecofriendly labelling (Chen et al, 2006). All were greatly understood and answered. Successfully the response rate was 100%.

3.1 Environmental Perceived Quality

The researchers have gone through the researches of major researchers (Zeithaml, 1988; Sweeney et al., 1999; Yoo and Donthu, 2001) to develop the scale to measure this research variable. The value of Cronbach's alpha is .851 which is acceptable as per

3.2 Environmental Perceived Risk

For this research variable, the researchers have gone through the previous researches of (Peter, Ryan, 1976; Jacoby and Kaplan, 1972; Murphy and Enis, 1986; Sweeney et al. 1999). The value of Cronbach's alpha is .847 which is acceptable as per standards.

3.3 Environmental Satisfaction

For this research variable, the researchers have gone through the previous researches of (Chen 2010). The value of Cronbach's alpha is .885 which is acceptable as per standards.

3.4 Environmental Trust

For this research variable, the researchers have gone through the previous researches of (Chen 2010). The value of Cronbach's alpha is .917 which is acceptable as per standards.

3. Analysis and Discussions

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

To test the proposed hypothesis, the researcher used Structural Equation Modeling. Furthermore, researchers applied SPSS and AMOS. In this study, descriptive analysis shows the different means and standard deviation of variables. The descriptive statistics also describes the minimum and maximum values of different variables used in this study. The descriptive statistics were shown in table 1.

Table: 1 Descriptive

items		Frequency	Percentage %
Gender	Male	56	56%
	Female	44	44%
Age	Min	23 years	
	Max	36 years	
Profession	Employee	6	6%
	Student	94	94%

This section contains the analysis of questionnaire as well as variables. The mean value of EPQ is 3.684 and standard deviation is 0.572 which means that EPQ can deviate from mean to both sides by .57. This paper uses Pearson's Correlation analysis to analyze the association between the variables and the direction of that relationship which is indicated in table 2. The correlation matrix indicates that EPQ is positively correlated with ES and ET as well, although there is a negative correlation between EPR and other variables.

Table 2
Mean, STD Deviation and Pearson's Correlation Matrix

	Mean	Std .Deviation	1	2	3	4
Perceived Quality	3.684	0.572	(.851)			
Perceived Risk	2.541	0.563	-0.368*	(.847)		
Satisfaction	3.747	0.578	0.379*	-0.354*	(.885)	
Trust	3.783	0.582	0.380**	-0.370*	0.388*	(.917)

Correlation is significant at ** $p < .01$, Correlation is significant at * $p < .05$, Alpha reliabilities in parentheses.

Table 3 indicates the consequences of Structural Equation Modeling that were used in this study. The whole measure of model in Structural Equation Modeling specifies that the model is valid and acceptable. (Degree of freedom =145, Chi Square = 290.6, Goodness of fit index (GFI) = 0.9, Root mean square of error approximation (RMSEA) =0.04, NFI =0.91, Comparative fit index (CFI) =0.918). All of estimated paths are significant, acceptable & hypothesis used in this research paper are supported. Therefore, H1, H2 and H3 all hypotheses were accepted. EPQ encounter both the severe environmental rules and regulations but also prevalent consumer ecology and environmentalism, and enrich ES and ET. Especially in Pakistan the corporate and strategic managers they should have to give proper attention to protect the environment.

Table 3
Structural Equation Modeling – Results

Hypothesis	Influence	Path Measurement	Outcome
1	Positive	0.289*	Supported
2	Negative	0.268*	Supported
3	Positive	0.260*	Supported

4. Findings and Conclusion

The present research has major findings and implications in the areas of research variables. The researchers have performed the in-depth analysis with various statistical methods to come up with the major practical implication. The previous literature does not determine how ET is built and how to maintain it. Consequently, the present research drives two constructs. Furthermore, EPR is negatively related to ES, so with the reduction of perceived risk consumers are more eager to purchase and get satisfied with the product and companies can then enhance ET.

This study also combines the literature on relationship marketing and green marketing to establish a ground framework of ET. These areas of are of the most importance in the year 2021 not only for the researchers but also for various sectors. According to empirical results, we conclude that companies should enhance EPQ, decrease the EPR and increase their ES to enhance ET in environmental scenario. In addition to above argument, perceived risk is crucial at identifying consumers, behavior because they are motivated to reduce perceived risk to maximize the purchase process (Rao et al, 2007). EPR always lowers the ES and ET, which leads to the understanding that marketers must eliminate the factor of risk at every point of opportunity. This finding may help various sectors not only minimize their present risks but also help in taking calculated risks.

4.1 Academic Contributions

Based on the data analysis and key findings, the present research has number of academic contributions. Firstly, the present research focuses on the relationship and green marketing into the decision-making perspective of ET. Secondly, sometimes customers are required to tradeoff among quality of product and environmental issues regarding product. Resultantly, customer will not sacrifice their needs and desire about quality of product just for environmental sake. More customers prefer their needs to the environmental concerns. The present research elaborates the environmental issues regarding perceived quality and perceived risk. Such framework has the

tendency to enhance ET in consumer's market. Finally, the present research explores the study of consumer's satisfaction, trust, perceived quality and perceived risk in the arena of marketing.

This study has promoted the ET in the arena of ecological and environmental management, demonstrating that EPQ and EPR are significantly related to ET. In this study, there are few practical contributions as well. First, the study explores that the increase in EPQ and EPR not only enhance customer's ES but also raise the ET of companies. Secondly, companies need to develop and enhance ES of their customers. For this purpose, companies can build ES from the customers to raise the level of encouraging relationship between EPQ and satisfaction, to reduce the level of destructive relationship between EPR and satisfaction in order to enhance the ET.

5. Future Research

This research has a major contribution in the said areas and based on this research, future research may be conducted with a larger sample size in different sector. This study deliberates and concentrates on electronics and automobile products in Pakistan. This contribution paves the way for the future researchers to concentrate on other kinds of products as well. Furthermore, the social context also influences consumer decision making. Different customers and consumers have different social backgrounds and influences.

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